

Mariene & Wasmuth; Genome assembly variation and its implications for gene discovery in nematode species

GENOME ASSEMBLY COMMANDS

Commands used, replace anything in square brackets [] with your appropriate path or unique name

Commands to assemble preliminary long read assemblies

*C.bovis* and *H.contortus* assemblies

Canu:

For *C.bovis*:

```
canu -p [UNIQUE_NAME] -d [UNIQUE_NAME] genomeSize=62.7m useGrid=true  
gridOptions="--time=24:00:00" -nanopore [PATH/TO/READS]
```

For *H.contortus*:

```
canu -p [UNIQUE_NAME] -d [UNIQUE_NAME] genomeSize=283.4 m useGrid=true  
gridOptions="--time=24:00:00" -pacbio [PATH/TO/READS]
```

Flye:

For *C.bovis*:

```
flye --nano-raw [PATH/TO/READS] --out-dir [UNIQUE_NAME] --threads [12]
```

For *H.contortus*

```
flye --pacbio-raw [PATH/TO/READS] --out-dir [UNIQUE_NAME] --threads [12]
```

Redbean (also known as wtdbg2):

For *C.bovis*:

```
wtdbg2 -x ont -g 62.7m -t [8] -i [PATH/TO/READS] -o [UNIQUE_NAME]  
wtpoa-cns -t [8] -i [UNIQUE_NAME].ctg.lay.gz -o [UNIQUE_NAME]
```

For *H.contortus*:

```
wtdbg2 -x ont -g 283.4m -t [8] -i [PATH/TO/READS] -o [UNIQUE_NAME]  
wtpoa-cns -t [8] -i [UNIQUE_NAME].ctg.lay.gz -o  
[UNIQUE_NAME]
```

SMARTdenovo:

```
smartdenovo.pl -p [UNIQUE_NAME] -c 1 [PATH/TO/READS] > [UNIQUE_NAME].mak  
make -f [UNIQUE_NAME].mak  
wtcns -t 16 < [UNIQUE_NAME].dmo.lay > [UNIQUE_NAME].fasta
```

Falcon:

Modify the default configuration file according to compute environment and input file:

Input

[General]

input_fofn=input.fofn ## Your list of paths to the input fasta files

input_type=raw

pa_DBdust_option= ## By default, dusting is turned on

pa_fasta_filter_option=streamed-median

target=assembly

skip_checks=False

LA4Falcon_preload=false

Data Partitioning

Large genomes(>10Mb)

pa_DBsplit_option=-x500 -s200

ovlp_DBsplit_option=-s200

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```
##### Repeat Masking
pa_HPCTANmask_option=
#no-op repmask param set
pa_REPmask_code=0,300;0,300;0,300
#####Pre-assembly
## adjust to your genome size
genome_size = 62726283 ## for C.bovis
## OR genomesize = 283439308 ## for H.contortus
seed_coverage = 40
length_cutoff = -1
pa_HPCdaligner_option=-v -B128 -M24
pa_daligner_option= -k18 -e0.80 -l3000 -h256 -w8 -s100
falcon_sense_option=--output-multi --min-idt 0.70 --min-cov 4 --max-
    n-read 400
falcon_sense_greedy=False
#####Pread overlapping
ovlp_HPCdaligner_option=-v -B128 -M24
ovlp_daligner_option= -k24 -e.94 -l3000 -h1024 -s100
#####Final Assembly
length_cutoff_pr=1000
overlap_filtering_setting=--max-diff 100 --max-cov 100 --min-cov 2
fc_ovlp_to_graph_option=
[job.defaults]
job_type=slurm
pwatcher_type=blocking
JOB_QUEUE=[settings for your default job queue/partition]
MB=300 ## memory allocated per job
NPROC=16 ## number of processors per job
njobs=10 ## number of concurrently running jobs
submit = srun --wait=0 -p {JOB_QUEUE} \ ## for slurm use srun
-J ${JOB_NAME}          \
-o ${JOB_STDOUT}        \
-e ${JOB_STDERR}       \
--mem-per-cpu=${MB}M \
--ntasks 1             \
--cpus-per-task=${NPROC} \
${JOB_SCRIPT}
## Running Falcon
##create file of file names
readlink -f [READS] > input.fofn
fc_run [UNIQUE_CONGIG_NAME].cfg

## Falcon-unzip:
##Falcon-unzip config file:
[General]
    max_n_open_files = 500
[Unzip]
    input_fofn=input.fofn
    input_bam_fofn=input_bam.fofn
    polish_include_zmw_all_subreads = true
```

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```
[job.defaults]
job_type=slurm
pwatcher_type=blocking
JOB_QUEUE=[settings for your default job queue/partition]
MB=300
NPROC=4
njobs=8
submit = srun --wait=0 -p ${JOB_QUEUE} \
-J ${JOB_NAME} \
-o ${JOB_STDOUT} \
-e ${JOB_STDERR} \
--mem-per-cpu=${MB}M \
--cpus-per-task=${NPROC} \
${JOB_SCRIPT}
##Running Falcon-unzip
readlink -f *.fasta > input.fofn
readlink -f *.bam > input_bam.fofn
fc_unzip.py [UNIQUE_CONGIG_NAME].cfg

##Preliminary assemblies for H.bakeri
## Hicanu
canu -assemble -p [UNIQUE_NAME]-d [UNIQUE_NAME] genomeSize=696.9m
useGrid=true cnsMemory=64 batMemory=62 gridOptions="--time=7-00:00:00" -
pacbio-hifi [PATH/TO/READS]

## Hifiasm
hifiasm -o [UNIQUE_NAME] -t 24 [PATH/TO/READS]

## Flye
flye --pacbio-hifi [PATH/TO/READS] --out-dir [UNIQUE_NAME] --threads [12]

DECONTAMINATION AND POLISHING ASSEMBLIES

## Mapping of the long reads to assemblies using Minimap2
minimap2 -ax map-ont \ ## use -ax map-pb for H.contortus
[PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] [PATH/TO/READS] > [UNIQUE_NAME].sam
# Sorting the alignments
samtools view -b [UNIQUE_NAME].sam | sort > [UNIQUE_NAME].sorted.bam
samtools index [UNIQUE_NAME].sorted.bam

## Running Diamond
# Extract and concatenate taxid mapping files from NCBI
echo "accession\taccession.version\ttaxid\tgti" >
reference_proteomes.taxid_map
zcat */*.idmapping.gz | grep "NCBI_TaxID" | awk '{print $1 "\t" $1 "\t" $3
"\t" 0}' >> reference_proteomes.taxid_map

wget -N ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pub/taxonomy/taxdump.tar.gz
```

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```
mkdir -p taxdump && tar xzf taxdump.tar.gz -C ./taxdump
```

Make diamond blast database with taxonomic information

```
diamond makedb --in [concatenated-reference_proteomes.fasta.gz] --taxonmap  
reference_proteomes.taxid_map \  
--taxonnodes [PATH/TO/taxdump/nodes.dmp] --db reference_proteomes.dmnd
```

```
diamond blastx --query [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] \  
--db [PATH/TO/reference_proteomes.dmnd] \  
--outfmt 6 qseqid staxids bitscore qseqid sseqid pident length mismatch  
gapopen qstart qend sstart send evalue bitscore \  
--max-target-seqs 1 --evaluate 1e-25 -o [UNIQUE_NAME].tsv --very-sensitive
```

Running BlobTools

```
blobtools map2cov -i [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] \  
--bam [PATH/TO/MINIMAP2_SORTED_BAM_FILE] -o [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_COVERAGE_FILE]
```

```
blobtools create -i [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] -t [PATH/TO/DIAMOND_OUTPUT_FILE.tsv]  
\  
--db [PATH/TO/BLOBTOOLS/nodesDB.txt] -x bestsumorder \  
--cov [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_COVERAGE_FILE] -o [UNIQUE_NAME]
```

Mapping and polishing decontaminated assemblies

Aligning the long reads to the filtered assembly using minimap2 and performing four rounds of racon.

```
minimap2 -ax map-ont \  
## use -ax map-pb for H. contortus  
[PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] [PATH/TO/READS] > [UNIQUE_NAME].sam
```

```
racon -m 8 -x -6 -g -8 -w 500 -t 16 [PATH/TO/READS] \  
[PATH/TO/MINIMAP_OUTPUT.sam] \  
[PATH/TO/BLOBTOOLS_OUPUT.fasta]  
> [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_RACON_ROUNDS].fasta
```

Repeat these steps four times with the output from the first round as input for the second round and so on. After the fourth round then:

For *C. bovis*: Polishing racon_round4.fasta using Medaka.

```
medaka_consensus -i [PATH/TO/READS] \  
-d [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND4.fasta] \  
-o [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_MEDAKA_CONSENSUS] -t 24 -m r941_min_high_g303
```

For *H. contortus*: Polishing racon_round4.fasta using Arrow.

First map using pbmm2

```
pbmm2 align [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND4.fasta] \  
[PATH/TO/HCONTORTUS_SUBREADS.bam] \  
[UNIQUE_OUTPUT_NAME].bam --sort -j 12 -J 4
```

```
pbindex [UNIQUE_OUTPUT_NAME].bam
```

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Running Arrow

```
samtools faidx [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND4.fasta]
```

```
arrow -j 32 [PATH/TO/PBMM2_OUTPUT.bam] -r [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND4.fasta] \  
-o [UNIQUE_OUTPUT_NAME].gff -o [UNIQUE_OUTPUT_NAME].fasta
```

Mapping Illumina short reads to the Medaka/Arrow polished assemblies using BWA-MEM and performing two iterations of racon.

For *C.bovis*: bwa index [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_MEDAKA_CONSENSUS].fasta

For *H.contortus*: bwa index [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_ARROW_OUPUT].fasta

```
bwa mem -t 24 [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_MEDAKA_CONSENSUS].fasta ## Or for  
H.contortus:[UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_ARROW_OUPUT].fasta  
[PATH/TO/ILLUMINA/SHORT/READS] > [UNIQUE_NAME].sam
```

```
racon -m 8 -x -6 -g -8 -w 500 -t 24 \  
[PATH/TO/ILLUMINA/SHORT/READS] \  
[PATH/TO/BWA-MEM_OUTPUT].sam \  
[UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_MEDAKA_CONSENSUS].fasta \  
## Or for  
H.contortus:[UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_ARROW_OUPUT].fasta  
> [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_RACON_ROUNDS].fasta
```

Repeat these steps two times with the output from the first round as input for the second round. After the second round then:

Performing two iterations of pilon on the racon_round2.fasta assembly.

```
bwa index [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND2.fasta]
```

```
bwa mem -t 8 [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND2.fasta] \  
[PATH/TO/ILLUMINA_READ1] [PATH/TO/ILLUMINA_READ2 | samtools sort -O bam \  
-o [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_SORTED].bam -T [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_TEMP_FILE]
```

```
samtools index [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_SORTED].bam
```

```
java -Xmx60G -jar pilon-1.24.jar \  
--genome [PATH/TO/RACON_ROUND2.fasta] --fix bases --frags  
[PATH/TO/SORTED/BAM/FILE]  
--threads 24 --output [UNIQUE_NAME_PILON_ROUNDS] | tee  
[UNIQUE_NAME_PILON_ROUNDS]
```

Repeat these steps two times with the output from the first round as input for the second round.

HAPLOTYPE DUPLICATION REMOVAL

Purge_dups commands and parameters

```
pri_asm=[PATH/TO/PRIMARY/ASSEMBLY].fasta
```

```
pb_fasta=[PATH/TO/READS]
```

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```
ref_genome_split=[PATH/TO/SPLIT/PRIMARY/ASSEMBLY].split.fasta  
self_aln_genome=[PATH/TO/SELF/ALIGNED/SPLIT/PRIMARY/ASSEMBLY].split.self.paf.gz
```

Running minimap2 to align pacbio data and generating paf files, then calculating read depth histogram and base-level read depth

```
minimap2 -I 6G -x map-pb $pri_asm $pb_fasta | gzip -c - > purge.paf.gz
```

Producing PB.base.cov and PB.stat files

```
[PATH/TO/BIN/pbcstat] [ALL].paf.gz  
[PATH/TO/BIN/CALCUTS PB.stat] > cutoffs 2> calcults.log  
python [PATH/TO/SCRIPTS/hist_plot.py -c cutoffs PB.stat PB.png
```

Splitting the primary assembly and doing a self-self alignment

```
[PATH/TO/BIN/split_fa $pri_asm > $pri_asm.split.fa  
[PATH/TO/BIN/split_fa $pri_asm > $ref_genome_split
```

```
minimap2 -x asm5 -DP $ref_genome_split $ref_genome_split | gzip -c - >  
$self_aln_genome
```

Purging haplotigs and overlaps

```
[PATH/TO/BIN/purge_dups -2 -T cutoffs -c PB.base.cov $self_aln_genome >  
dups.bed 2> purge_dups.log
```

Getting purged primary and haplotig sequences from draft assembly

```
[PATH/TO/BIN/get_seqs dups.bed $pri_asm > [PURGED_ASSEMBLY].fa 2>  
[HAPLOTIG_SEQUENCES].fa
```

ASSEMBLY EVALUATIONS

BUSCO command used to evaluate the completeness of single copy orthologues:

```
busco -i [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] --lineage nematoda_odb10 --out [UNIQUE_NAME] --  
mode genome --long -augustus
```

Additionally, we assessed the alignment of sequence reads to each assembled genome using Inspector

For this evaluation, we used the raw ONT reads for the *C. bovis* assemblies, the raw PacBio RS and Sequel reads for the *H. contortus* assemblies, and the raw HiFi long reads for the *H. bakeri* assemblies.

Inspector commands used to align sequence reads to assemblies to identify both large- and small-scale errors.

```
inspector.py --thread 24 --contig [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY] --read [PATH/TO/READS] -  
-outpath [UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_OUTPUT_DIRECTORY] --datatype [nanopore for C. bovis  
or clr for H. contortus or hifi for H. bakeri].
```

To generate the corrected assembly

```
inspector-correct.py --thread 24 --inspector  
[UNIQUE_NAME_FOR_OUTPUT_DIRECTORY] --datatype [nano-raw or pacbio-raw or  
pacbio-hifi] --outpath [DIRECTORY_FOR_CORRECTED_ASSEMBLY].
```

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GENOME SYNTENY

```
## Genome-to-genome alignments of the final draft assemblies using the Nucmer
nucmer --maxmatch --prefix=[UNIQUE_NAME] [REFERENCE GENOME] [QUERY GENOME]
```

```
## For the C. bovis, we used the dnadiff wrapper script to report one-to-one
alignment coordinates
dnadiff -d [NUCMER_OUTPUT].delta
```

```
## For all the generated assemblies, we used NucDiff to quantify the
structural and local genome differences between each assembly and its
respective reference genome
nucdiff --proc 24 --ref_name_full yes --query_name_full yes [REFERENCE
GENOME] [QUERY GENOME] [PREFIX NAME]
```

GENE PREDICTION

```
##RNA-seq data alignment using STAR (For H. contortus and H. bakeri)
STAR --runThreadN [24] --runMode genomeGenerate \
  --genomeDir [DIRECTORY_FOR_ASSEMBLY_INDEX]
  --genomeFastaFiles [PATH/TO/ASSEMBLY]
```

Mapping RNA-seq reads

```
STAR --genomeDir [ASSEMBLY_INDEX_DIRECTORY] --readFilesCommand zcat \
  --readFilesIn [INPUT RNA-SEQ READS] --runThreadN [20] \
  --outSAMtype BAM Unsorted \
  --outFileNamePrefix [UNIQUE_NAME]
```

Sorting the aligned RNA-seq bam file

```
samtools sort [UNIQUE_NAME.bam] --threads [20] -o [UNIQUE_NAME_sorted.bam] -T
tmp.bam
```

BRAKER 3 RUN

```
export BRAKER_SIF=[PATH/TO/SINGULARITY/CONTAINER]
export GENEMARK_PATH=[PATH/TO/GENEMARK]
export PATH=[PATH/TO/PROTHINT/BIN]:$PATH
```

```
singularity exec -B $PWD:$PWD [PATH/TO/SINGULARITY/CONTAINER] \
cp -r /usr/share/augustus/config $PWD/.augustus \
singularity exec -B $PWD:$PWD [PATH/TO/SINGULARITY/CONTAINER] \
braker.pl --AUGUSTUS_CONFIG_PATH=$PWD/.augustus \
  --species=[SPECIES_NAME] --threads=24 --softmasking \
  --genome=[PATH/TO/SOFTMASKED/GENOME] \
  --GENEMARK_PATH=[PATH/TO/GENEMARK]
  --bam=[PATH/TO/SORTED/RNA-SEQ.bam] ## For H. contortus and H. bakeri
  --prot_seq=[PATH/TO/PROTEIN/SEQS.fasta] ## For C. bovis
  --PROTHINT_PATH=[PATH/TO/PROTHINT/BIN] ## For C. bovis
```

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